

GROUNDING SYSTEM IMPEDANCE MEASUREMENT - CASE STUDY

Vojin KOSTIĆ¹, Nebojša RAIČEVIĆ², Jovan MRVIĆ³ and Slavica REBRIĆ⁴

Abstract: The measurement of grounding system impedance of an energized substation is usually required. Consequently, the power system frequency interference and harmonic frequencies may adversely affect the measurement. In order to improve the signal-to-interference ratio, we can increase the intensity of the test current or the test current frequency should be slightly different from the power system frequency. In the latter case, so called *Frequency Shift Method* (FSM), the intensity of test current may be relatively low. In this paper, we empirically examine the sufficient intensity of the test current. The corresponding field test in the 220/110/10 kV substation is described.

Keywords: Grounding system impedance, measurements, interference, heavy-current injection, frequency shift method.

INTRODUCTION

The main goals of high-voltage substation grounding systems are to provide: 1. safety conditions for personnel and general population in and around the yard of the substation, and 2. to minimize thermal and voltage stress on high-voltage equipment. Consequently, the grounding system of power facility should be adequately designed and tested [1] – [4]. Before test performing, indicators or indicative quantities should be defined that can be measured and then compared with established reference values predicted during the design phase [5] – [6]. The most common way of quantifying grounding system performance is grounding system impedance measurement. Measurements of grounding system impedance in high-voltage substations are inevitably related to the electromagnetic interference at power system frequency (50 Hz) and harmonic frequencies [7]. There are different mechanisms that interference affects measurement: stray currents in the grounding grid generated by the line asymmetry or unbalanced power system loads, magnetic field induction between voltage test leads and current test leads, electromagnetic field induced in the test leads from nearby high-voltage equipment which is in normal operating condition, and so on. This means there is a great possibility of interference superimposed to the measured quantities, which further leads to underestimation of grounding system impedance, and also an underestimation of ground potential rise under ground fault conditions.

To ensure reliable measurement result, a high signal-to-interference ratio (SIR) is required. Therefore the traditional measurement approach was based on the heavy-current injection method [8] -[9]. According to this method, large AC current at power system frequency is injected into the grounding system under test. Then the voltage between the

grounding system under test and the voltage probe is measured. However, this is not usually a practical option since a significant power source is required, especially in circumstances where the neighboring substation can not be used as a current probe. In such conditions, the grounding of a tower, which is distant enough, may be used as a current probe. The main problem is that the towers often do not have a low resultant impedance to earth. Nowadays, new test equipment is available that can accurately characterize a grounding system without the need for large current injection.

An alternative measurement approach is based on the test current at a frequency slightly different from the power system frequency - *Frequency Shift Method* (FSM). We have described this method in [10] – [11]. It has been shown that the FSM is insensitive to time-varying interference. In this paper, we will further elaborate the FSM. In fact, we will examine the minimum required intensity of the test current.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II briefly presents the measurement setup and procedures. In section III we present results from measurements performed at the high-voltage substation 220/110/10 kV (Valjevo 3, Serbia). Concluding remarks are given in section IV.

PRINCIPLES OF MEASUREMENT

The FSM measurement setup is depicted in Fig. 1. A key part of the measurement setup is the variable frequency current source (California Instruments, type 15001iM), which is based on the combining of the variable frequency, voltage and current functions.

Fig.1 – Measurement setup for FSM.

In order to examine the sensitivity of the FSM to the intensity of the test current, we have performed the experiment for two quite different test current intensity. First, we

¹ Electrical Engineering Institute Nikola Tesla, University of Belgrade, Koste Glavinića 8a, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia, e-mail: vojin@iecent.org

² University of Niš, Faculty of Electronic Engineering, Aleksandra Medvedeva 14, 18000 Niš, Serbia, e-mail: nebojsa.raicevic@elfak.ni.ac.rs

³ Electrical Engineering Institute Nikola Tesla, University of Belgrade, Koste Glavinića 8a, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia, e-mail: jovan.mrvic@iecent.org

⁴ PE Elektromreža Srbije, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia, e-mail: slavica.rebric@ems.rs

will inject the test current about 23 A r.m.s. at different test frequencies (40 Hz, 60 Hz and 75 Hz). From now on, this experiment is referred to as a *high - current experiment*. Then, we will inject test current about 4 A r.m.s. at different test frequencies (40 Hz, 60 Hz and 75 Hz). This experiment is referred to as a *low - current experiment*.

A high – voltage (110 kV) overhead line was used as a current test line between the grounding system under test and the auxiliary grounding system. The auxiliary grounding system is 4 km far away. The overhead shield wire was connected to the measured grounding system, so the reduction factor, r , should be taken into account. The ground potential rise (GPR) was measured by a rod which was driven into the ground at the reference point and a voltage lead which connects this rod to the oscilloscope. The reference point is considered to be sufficiently far, when the variation in GPR with increasing distance becomes small enough.

The monitoring of the ground potential and test current waveforms was done by two-channel oscilloscope. The recording of these signals was performed by the acquisition software loaded on a laptop computer. Typical waveforms for *high-current experiment* and *low-current experiment* are shown in Figs.2 and 3 respectively. These distorted waveforms, which are a direct consequence of high levels of electromagnetic interference, indicate the necessity of FSM application in the grounding system impedance testing of a large-sized high-voltage substations.

Fig.2 – Typical oscillograms of injected current (red line) and measured voltage (green line) signals at 60 Hz for high-current experiment.

Fig.3 – Typical oscillograms of injected current (red line) and measured voltage (green line) signals at 60 Hz for low-current experiment.

Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) is used for the processing of the signals, which are further digitally filtered. The values of measured grounding system impedance are

obtained as the ratio of the DFT of the resulting GPR signal and the DFT of the injected current signal. This is done for the three test frequencies, f_1, f_2, f_3 . The obtained results are presented graphically ($Z(f_i)$ where $i=1,2,3$). In order to estimate the regression line, the standard software package is used to perform a linear regression between three $Z(f_i)$ points. From regression line was obtained the grounding system impedance at the power system frequency (50 Hz).

FIELD TEST RESULTS

The measurements of the grounding system impedance were performed in the interconnection high-voltage substation rated voltage 220/110/10 kV (Valjevo, Serbia) successively in two experiments: *low-current* and *high-current*. During the experiment, the substation was in normal operating condition.

Field test results presented in Table I clearly show that the ground potential signal after processing was higher than the power frequency interference voltage during the first experiment (see columns three and four), about 1.5 times the value. As one can see from Table II, the value of interference voltage signal was almost 4 times the value than the ground potential signal of interest for further analysis.

Graphical representation of the measurement results, as listed in Tables I and II, were shown in Figs. 2 to 5. It is obvious that grounding system impedance, resistance, reactance and impedance phase angle measurement results show very good correlation at all test frequencies (40 Hz, 60 Hz and 75 Hz). By performing linear regression between the three FSM measured points (for Z, R, X and θ separately) the corresponding regression line was obtained.

The grounding system impedance at the power system frequency was estimated from the regression line (green line, Figs. 4 and 5). The results for grounding system impedance at 50 Hz, for two experiments, were presented in Tables III and IV, respectively. The corresponding relative measurement errors were listed in Table V.

Table I
Test results for high-current experiment

f [Hz]	$r \cdot I(f)$ [A]	$U(f)$ [V]	U_i [V]	$Z(f)$ [Ω]	$\theta(f)$ [$^\circ$]	$R(f)$ [Ω]	$X(f)$ [Ω]
40	23.70	1.38	0.93	0.0583	0.17	0.0583	0.0002
60	23.54	1.33	0.94	0.0564	4.10	0.0563	0.0040
75	23.46	1.31	0.88	0.0558	7.44	0.0554	0.0072

LEGEND:

f - test current frequency; $I(f)$ - test current; r - reduction factor;

$U(f)$ - ground potential rise after processing;

U_i - ground potential rise at 50 Hz;

$Z(f)$ - impedance; $\theta(f)$ - impedance phase angle; $R(f)$ - resistance; $X(f)$ - reactance.

From Tables III and IV it's obvious that the grounding system impedance is predominantly resistive (one can see from Figs. 4 and 5 that the lines of regression functions are practically overlap). The value of reactance is negligible compared to the value of resistance.

The relative measurement error of the grounding system impedance (Z, R , and X), based on low test current and high test current, is mainly about 0.07%. The highest value of

relative measurement error is obtained for reactance (2.82%), but the value of reactance in both experiments is too low in comparison to the value of resistance. Therefore, we are positive that the FSM gives an accurate assessment of the grounding system impedance even with low-current injection and conditions where the interference signal is much higher than the signal of interest for further analysis.

Table II
Test results for low-current experiment.

f [Hz]	$r \cdot I(f)$ [A]	$U(f)$ [V]	U_i [V]	$Z(f)$ [Ω]	$\Theta(f)$ [$^\circ$]	$R(f)$ [Ω]	$X(f)$ [Ω]
40	3.95	0.2304	0.90	0.0583	0.53	0.0583	0.0005
60	4.10	0.2312	0.90	0.0563	3.76	0.0562	0.0037
75	4.05	0.2254	0.97	0.0556	7.10	0.0552	0.0069

LEGEND: AS IN TABLE I

Fig.4 – Graphical representation of the test results for high-current experiment.

Fig.5 – Graphical representation of the test results for low-current experiment

Fig.6 – Graphical representation of the test results for impedance phase angle (high-current experiment).

Fig.7 – Graphical representation of the test results for impedance phase angle (low-current experiment)

Table III
Test results for grounding system impedance at 50 Hz (high-current experiment)

Z [Ω]	R [Ω]	X [Ω]	Θ [$^\circ$]
0.05743	0.05736	0.00213	2.18

LEGEND: SEE TABLE I

Table IV
Test results for grounding system impedance at 50 Hz (low-current experiment)

Z [Ω]	R [Ω]	X [Ω]	Θ [$^\circ$]
0.05739	0.05732	0.00219	2.25

Table V
Relative measurement error

$Z_{relative}$ [%]	$R_{relative}$ [%]	$X_{relative}$ [%]	$\theta_{relative}$ [%]
0.07	0.07	2.82	3.21

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The measurement results presented in this paper indicate some important facts:

- Grounding system impedance active (resistance) and reactive (reactance) component, and also impedance phase angle can be easily obtained using FSM.
- The grounding system impedance of large-sized interconnection high-voltage substation is predominantly resistive and the value of reactance is practically negligible.
- Using FSM grounding system impedance of large-sized high-voltage substation ($>20000 \text{ m}^2$) can be obtained by injecting test current of only few amps.
- FSM is the accurate method even in situations where the signal (at 50 Hz)-to-interference ratio is low.

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